

DELIVERABLE

D8.1 Quality & Risk Plan

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0.1	12/08/2019	Milos Ulman	CULS	Initial draft
0.2	26/08/2019	Milos Ulman	CULS	Second reviewer added; a list of internal reviewers added (Annex 1); a draft of risk assessments added (Annex 2); Figure 1 Deliverable Approval Process added. Updates based on the reviewers' feedback were done as tracked changes. Table border lines were made more contrasting and font size in tables was consolidated.
0.3	28/08/2019	Milos Ulman	CULS	Annex 2 – Assessment of Critical Risks amended, new unforeseen risks added;
1.0	29/08/2019	Milos Ulman	CULS	Amendments to risks 13, 14, and 15; all tracked changes and comments removed; minor formatting changes.

Responsibility for the information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable details PoliRural's quality and risk monitoring plan. The success criteria are used to monitor the progress towards the project objectives and its expected impact. The project objectives and related success criteria defined in the Description of Action (DoA) are presented. The progress will be regularly monitored by the Steering Committee and reported to the REA in three Periodic Reports, and one Final Report delivered within the reporting periods as set by the Grant Agreement.

The Consortium ensures that the deliverables and any other documents produced in the lifetime of the project will be of the highest quality by introducing the Deliverable Quality Management process including the deliverable internal peer review and step-by-step approval split down in three phases of a 45-day Deliverable Approval Process. The list of internal expert reviewers of PoliRural deliverables is defined in the Annex 1.

The Consortium recognises that even the most perfectly drafted work plan can stumble upon risks, which can influence the project's outcomes. Therefore, the PoliRural partners have implemented the Continuous Risk Management approach and have used this methodology to identify multiple critical risks, to suggest mitigation measures and to perform the project's first risk assessment. The results of the critical risks assessment are reported in the Annex 2.

The risks will be continuously monitored throughout the lifetime of the project and the Consortium's initial risk assessment will be updated on a regular basis. Together with the progress on the success criteria, the updated risk assessment will be reported to the REA on four occasions during the project duration.

1 Introduction

Managing complex international projects such as PoliRural requires a well-defined project management and quality plan before any crucial work on the project may begin. The project management of PoliRural is built around tried and trusted techniques that are also reflected in an efficient management structure. This provides a coherent foundation for managing the PoliRural project in order to guarantee a dependable and straightforward project implementation and to ensure the highest quality of project outcomes. Next to it, the D8.1 Quality & Risk Plan complements the project management procedures by detailing the quality methodology, defining the process of the success criteria measurement, setting up deliverable quality assurance processes, as well as identifying risks PoliRural may encounter and describing mitigation measures the Consortium intends to take should they occur.

2 Objectives and Success Criteria

In order to achieve its objectives and provide the best quality in the day-to-day management of the tasks, PoliRural will apply a strict and regular quality assessment during the course of the project. This process is based on measurement progress towards PoliRural objectives by the means of the Success Criteria defined in the Part B of the Description of Action (DoA). This chapter presents the objectives and derived Success Criteria that have been defined in the DoA and the agreed methodology to monitor the progress towards their fulfilment.

Objective	Measurement	Success Criteria	Milestone
<i>1. Design a multi-governance policy innovation hub and European ecosystem which strengthens the evidence base for rural policy, making it truly participatory and forward looking</i>			
1.1 Build a strong enabling stakeholder community for the rural ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. regions engaged No. stakeholders involved No. new sign-ups Levels of interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12 regions 456 regional panel members 20% member increase per year 50+ opportunities for group exchange 	M1 M6
1.2 All regional stakeholders active in policy co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy makers involved Experts involved Male farmers or rural dwellers Female farmers or rural dwellers Male new entrants Female new entrants Level of participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 36+ policy makers 60+ experts 180+ male farmers or rural dwellers 60+ female farmers or rural dwellers 60+ new male entrants 60+ new female entrants 80% level of participation 	M3 M5 M6
1.3 Foster the cross-fertilisation of knowledge across regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. physical meetings No. virtual meetings Meeting attendance No. pilot cluster maps No. policy exporting regions No. policy importing regions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10 physical meetings 40 virtual meetings 100% attendance 5 pilot cluster maps 6 exporting regions 10 assimilating regions 	M2 M3 M5 M6
<i>2. Measure prevailing attitudes toward rural policies among regional stakeholders by unlocking extra insights from unstructured data</i>			

2.1 Unleash the benefits of text mining in rural policy making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of new data sources No. of languages covered No. of domain Named Entities (NE) Usefulness of Semantic Explorer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1800 new sources 12 languages 5000+ of NEs per language 80% acceptance rate 	M2 M3
2.2 Advance rural policy objectives by testing the tool on different occasions (needs gathering, policy evaluation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. sources in the 'needs' library No. sources in 'evaluation' library No. of case studies No. of opinions extracted No. of emotions extracted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 900-strong needs library 900-strong evaluation library 12 case studies on text mining - rural 100+ opinions per policy measure 10+ emotions per opinion 	M2 M3
<p>3. Explore the future trajectory of rural development in participating regions using a hybrid foresight approach (quantitative plus qualitative), taking into account both historic and current situation</p>			
3.1 Build a conceptual model of rural ecosystem using quantitative and qualitative methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of methods No. workshops No. of models created No. regional model versions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Both qualitative & quantitative 24 exploration & validation w/shops 1 core model 12 adapted regional models 	M1 M5
3.2 Translate concept into system dynamics to better understand underlying inter-relationship & impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of modules No. of indicators No. of scenarios Quality of insights Usefulness of insights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5+ available modules 20 key indicators 4 scenarios 90% accuracy 70%+ usefulness of simulation results 	M4
3.3 Promote the combined approach (system dynamics & scenario modelling) for advancing rural policy objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. regions completing approach No. policies analysed No. of outlook studies User experience/satisfaction No. new regions interested 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12 regions implementing approach 36+ regional policies analysed 12 regional outlook studies 70%+ satisfaction with results 6 new regions interested 	M6

4. Advance understanding of rural reality by existing rural populations and new entrants, and co-design interventions which make rural places and professions more accessible, attractive, equitable, resilient & competitive			
4.1 Investigate factors making rural places/professions more/less attractive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. needs-policies canvases • No. evaluation diagrams • No. rural-reality reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 regional, gender-sensitive canvases • 12 interactive evaluation radar charts • 12 rural-reality reports 	M2 M3
4.2 Contribute to the emerging corpus of knowledge on new entrants with new insights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New entrant database • No. new business & entry models • Visual storytelling • No. views case studies/stories • No. countries knowledge shared 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 new entrant case studies • 10+ new business & entry models • 12 videos on new entrant experiences • 20,000 views of material • 50+ countries viewing the Hub 	M2 M3 M6
4.3 Boost the attractiveness of rural places & professions through new or updated measures that empower under-represented groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of policy recommendations • No. adopted measures • No. measures promoting inclusion • Impact of the introduced measures • PoliRural ambassadors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 sets of policy recommendations • 12 new regional measures • 6+ measures geared toward women, young people or migrants • 70%+ usefulness from post evaluation • 15 PoliRural ambassadors 	M5 M6

Table 1 Success Criteria as defined in DoA

Next to the regular progress monitoring performed during monthly Steering Committee calls, the progress towards the Success Criteria targets will be measured and reported towards the REA on four occasions during the project as defined in the following table:

Success Criteria Measurement #	Project Month / Date	Reported to REA in	Related Project Milestone
1	M12 / June 2020	Periodic Report 1	MS1, MS2

2	M24 / June 2021	Periodic Report 2	MS3, MS4
3	M36 / June 2022	Periodic Report 3	MS5, MS6
4	M36 / June 2022	Final Report	MS5, MS6

Table 2 Success Criteria Measurement Schedule and Reporting

3 Deliverable Quality Management

During the whole project duration, the use of continuous quality management ensures that high quality outcomes from the Consortium are achieved. The progress of work within the Consortium will be monitored against the milestones, defined objectives and relevant success criteria. The Coordinator is responsible for the implementation of the PoliRural Deliverable Quality Management Process which is further detailed in the following chapter.

3.1 Deliverable Template

To ensure high quality of all the project's deliverables, the project management has provided a template that shall be used by all partners. The templates have been stored in Redmine¹, folder *Documents* in *DMSF* section of the PoliRural project. The deliverable template is provided in MS Word format. When working on a deliverable, the deliverable lead may also turn the template in a Google document for an efficient collaboration with other contributing partners and reviewers. At the end however, the deliverable must be downloaded and formatted offline in order to prepare the document for submission through SYGMA.

3.2 Deliverable Approval Process

In order to ensure the highest quality of the deliverables as well their timely production and submission, the Consortium has developed the Deliverable Approval Process (DAP). The DAP is in line with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, Article 6.6 Internal Quality Control, Monitoring and Reporting.

The following figure presents the DAP as a step-by-step procedure comprising three phases: Finalisation, Peer Review and Approval.

¹ <https://redmine.ccss.cz>

Figure 1 Deliverable Approval Process

Finalisation (45 to 15 days to delivery date)

The first step presents a 30-day long Finalisation phase which is conducted by the relevant Work Package Leader specified as a 'Lead Beneficiary' in the DoA Annex 1 - Part A. The WP Leader is responsible for initiating the work on that deliverable and a timely delivery of it to the second phase called Peer Review. However, WP Leader may remind a partner in charge of the deliverable to share ideas, draft, table of contents, but not doing all the work for the partner. WP Leader is empowered to request contributions towards a deliverable from the other partners when it is commonly agreed that a partner has expertise in a given field required for producing quality deliverables. In general, WP Leaders are autonomous in the way they organize the preparation of a deliverable. The project budget provides an indicative per-task breakdown of person-month to be invested by each of the partners.

The Finalisation phase starts with submission of the latest version of the deliverable and Deliverable Implementation and Availability Report (DIAR) prepared by the Deliverable Leader. DIAR specifies and assesses the progress of work for the relevant deliverable and indicates if that particular deliverable will be ready for submission to the Funding Authority in time. In practice, DIAR will take form of short notes written by the Deliverable Leader in Redmine during uploading the file. DIAR and the latest version of the deliverable should be available to the WP leader no later than 45 days before the deadline. The WP Leader reviews the DIAR and deliverable and provides comments to the Deliverable Leader within 15 days of receipt at the latest. If needed, after receiving comments from the WP Leader the Deliverable Leader amends the deliverable and submits it to the WP Leader for a review and approval no later than 30 days before the deadline. Once approved, the WP Leader shall submit the DIAR and a pre-final version of the deliverable for a peer review to the relevant manager and assistant manager no later than 15 days before the deadline for the respective deliverable

Peer Review (15 days to delivery date)

A peer review of the pre-final version of the deliverable is conducted until a common agreement is reached on the final document. Since only eight days are foreseen as sufficient for the peer review, it is strongly recommended to involve internal reviewers in the deliverable drafting process. This will allow to receive and incorporate reviewers' feedback in early stages of development. Once the reviewers finish their work, the WP Leader is also responsible for sharing the final document via the respective WP workspace in Redmine. This should be done at least seven days before the official deadline. At this point, the document enters the last and third phase called Approval.

Approval (7 days to delivery date)

Approval commences 7 days before the deliverable deadline. Once the Deliverable Leader uploads the final draft to the PoliRural workspace in Redmine, all partners may submit their feedback via Redmine within three days. After that, WP Leader will implement last updates, approve the document and submit the final version to Redmine. The final approval is done by the Manager and Coordinator who will also subsequently submit the deliverable to the REA.

3.3 Deliverable Internal Review

To ensure the highest possible quality of project outcomes, each deliverable will undergo an internal peer review performed by reviewers selected from within the Consortium. The internal reviewers who are listed in the Annex 1 shall be involved in the deliverable drafting process before the deliverables is submitted for approval to the Coordinator. The Deliverable Leader is responsible for contacting specified reviewing partners and ensuring the deliverable is accepted by them before the deliverable is sent out for the approval. Therefore, each document will be reviewed by at least two reviewers should assess the quality of the deliverable in question and request modifications if necessary.

3.4 Deliverables Versioning

The WP Leader together with the Deliverable Leader are responsible for storing each new version of the deliverable in the respective issue workspace on Redmine. Each version of the deliverable should be numbered in order to allow the Coordinator and other project partners to follow the work progress as well as to allow contributions from the involved partners. To simplify the orientation in multiple versions of the document, the WP Leader shall name and number the versions and these saved versions shall be in line with the Revision History table of the deliverable. A date shall be included next to the version number such as in the following example: *D8.1_QR_Plan_v0.1_120819.docx*

The draft versions of a deliverable shall be numbered v0.1, v0.2 and so on resulting in the final version 1.0 which is sent to the European Commission. As soon as a draft version of a deliverable is approved by the Coordinator it will no longer be modifiable and will be saved as the final version. Any changes requested afterwards would generate a new version of the deliverable, e.g. v1.1, with an associated new version number and a record justifying the need and reason for change. All the above-described versions of a deliverable shall be listed in the Revision History table at the beginning of the deliverable.

4 Risk Management

An essential component of the PoliRural project management is risk management. Since PoliRural is a research and innovative project, there is a considerable level of risk associated with the project. A risk is seen as a possibility of exposure to unfavourable circumstance affecting the successful completion of PoliRural. To alleviate the possible negative effects of unforeseen circumstances, PoliRural risk management provides processes for the evaluation and control of potential project risks with a special attention put on diagnosis and preventive action. The objective is to avoid unjustified project interruptions, budget excess, uncontrollable time or scheduling extensions and to steer the project to a full achievement of objectives set out in DoA. The risk management plan is thus set up at the start of the project to clearly define how the Consortium will manage risks throughout the project lifetime.

This plan includes a risk log where individual critical risks are identified. The risk log will be an informal document that will be regularly updated and amended to take into account any new circumstances and the latest situation as the project evolves. The risk log will be discussed at Steering Committee calls and/or General Assemblies. WP leaders can share any concerns they may have about tasks in their work package, with contribution from other partners.

4.1 Continuous Risk Management Approach

Overall, the risk management plan allows to predict risks that would have an adverse impact on the project such as increased costs, delays in terms of delivery, reduced quality of the end service(s), diminished market share, and so forth. Risk management involves:

- Continuous assessment of risks;
- Identifying which risks could have a negative impact on the project and have to be tackled;
- Recognizing and identifying mitigation strategies to diminish the risks.

The elements of continuous risk management approach include the following steps: *Figure 2 Continuous Risk Management Approach*

- 1) **Identify** – The project risks are identified before they become problems;
- 2) **Analyse** – Transforming identified risks into data for decision-making;
- 3) **Plan** – Transforming risk information into decision and mitigation activities and their implementation;
- 4) **Track** – Continuous tracking and monitoring of risk indicators and mitigation strategies;
- 5) **Control** – Implementation of eventual corrections from the risk mitigation plans;
- 6) **Communicate** – Communication between the project partners about the current status.

4.2 Risk Monitoring Responsibility

WP Leaders are responsible for closely monitoring the already identified risks in their respective WPs and implementing the mitigation measures as well as to screen for possible new risks. They shall immediately report to the Steering Committee. The most critical risks shall be given special attention during risk monitoring.

Management of external risks will be the responsibility of the Steering Committee based on the input from all Consortium partners. Timely awareness of and reaction to potential problems will be crucial to effective risk management.

The Coordinator will continuously assess project risks based on input from the PoliRural members and will maintain the risks and mitigations plan. Appropriate corrective actions will be taken if necessary and tracked to completion to avoid or reduce the impact of any risk detected.

4.3 Risk Assessment

Based on the above-described methodology, the Consortium has identified a set of critical risks and suggested mitigation measures. The PoliRural Consortium has considered internal as well as external risks to the project.

Together with the identification of the risk and related mitigation measures, the WP leaders have also performed the first risk assessment by the end of the second month of the project by indicating:

- i. whether any risk mitigation measures have been applied, and
- ii. whether the risk have materialized.

Identified Risks

The identified critical risks, mitigation measures and their assessment by the end of the second month of the project are provided in Annex 2.

Please note that next to the risks identified already at the PoliRural proposal-writing and grant preparation stage which have become part of the DoA, several additional risks have been identified in the first two months of the project as intense project work started. These risks have been uploaded to the Critical Risks section of the Funding and Tenders Portal via the Continuous Reporting module

4.4 Reporting on the Critical Risks Status

Once a risk has been identified, it will be tracked and monitored throughout the course of the project in order to minimise the potential damage it may cause. This will be done through Periodic Reports. This method will be based on determining risk prioritisation using probability and impact factors.

The risk assessment will be regularly reported to the EC's Funding and Tenders Portal in the module Continuous Reporting. Moreover, the updated risk log with the updated assessment will be submitted to the REA as a part of the reports summarized in Table 3.

Risk Report #	Project Month / Date	Reported to REA in	Related Project Milestone
1	M12 / June 2020	Periodic Report 1	MS1, MS2
2	M24 / June 2021	Periodic Report 2	MS3, MS4
3	M36 / June 2022	Periodic Report 3	MS5, MS6
4	M36 / June 2022	Final Report	MS5, MS6

Table 3 Schedule of the Risk Assessment Reporting

5 Conclusion

A complex, international project such as PoliRural cannot be achieved without a predefined and efficient quality and risk management plans.

The D8.1 Quality & Risk Plan provides a consolidated list of the project's success criteria matched with project objectives and describes their measurement and reporting towards the REA.

The high quality of PoliRural deliverables is secured by the three-phase methodology on deliverable approval, which also includes an internal peer review.

Risk-avoidance is an important issue for the PoliRural Consortium and has been treated as such. The Consortium has ensured that this document covers all critical risks, which have been identified at this early stage of the project to prevent any potential threat to the project's expected outcomes. The PoliRural partners have developed the Continuous Risk Management Approach and used it not only to identify multiple risks, but also to suggest mitigation measures and perform the first risk assessment in the project.

All WPs will be regularly monitored by the WP Leaders to detect previously unidentified risks before they occur. When new risks emerge, both the risk management plan and mitigation measures will be updated in order to ensure the successful delivery of project results.

The progress towards objectives measured by means of the success criteria and status of the critical risks will be assessed regularly and reported to the REA at four occasions linked to the project periodic reports and milestones.

Annex 1: Deliverable Internal Reviewers

Deliverable #	Deliverable Title	WP	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissem. Level	Due Date (in months)	Internal Reviewers
D1.1	PoliRural Vision For Attractive Rural Places & Professions	WP1	AREI	Report	Public	2	Pavel Kogut (21C), Pavel Šimek (CULS)
D1.2	PoliRural Framework: Concepts, Methods, Innovation	WP1	21C	Report	Public	3	Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA), Christian Hartmann (JIIP), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Denis Kolokol (KAJO)
D7.1	Communication & Dissemination Plan	WP7	SPI	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	3	Pavel Kogut (21C), Pavel Šimek (CULS)
D8.1	Quality & Risk Plan	WP8	CULS	Report	Public	3	Pavel Kogut (21C), Uri Marchaim (MIGAL)
D2.1	Text Mining Technical Specifications	WP2	KAJO	Report	Public	4	Antoni Oliva Quesada (22SISTEMA), Anne Gobin (VITO)
D3.1	Innovation Hub Technical Specifications	WP3	CCSS	Report	Public	4	Runar Bergheim (AVINET), Pavel Kogut (21C)
D7.2, D7.13, D7.14, D7.15	Practice Abstracts	WP7	SPI	Report	Public	6,12,18,28	Susie McAleer (21C), Věra Motyčková (CULS)
D8.2	Data Management Plan	WP8	P4A	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Public	6	Zuzana Pálková (SUA), Nikolaos Marianos (NP)
D1.3	Needs Gathering & Policy Mapping Template	WP1	JIIP	Report	Public	6	Pavel Kogut (21C), Christian Hartmann (JIIP), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Denis

							Kolokol (KAJO), Konstantinos Meletis (Perifereia), Laila Gercane (VPR), Nicola Faccilongo (Innovagritech), Petra Korkiakoski (HAMK)
D4.1	Regional Library For Needs Analysis	WP4	NÚVIT	Other	Public	6	Petra Korkiakoski (HAMK), Anita Selicka (LLF)
D5.1	PoliRural Model (ed. 1)	WP5	22SISTEMA	Report	Public	6	Virpi Oskman (JIIP), Jesús Estrada (TRAGSA)
D2.2	Prototype Text Mining Solution	WP2	KAJO	Demonstrator	Public	7	Karel Charvat (CCSS), Runar Bergheim (AVINET)
D4.2	Grassroot Needs & Factors Of Rural Attractiveness	WP4	TRAGSA	Report	Public	9	John O'Flaherty (MAC), Antonia Oliva (22SISTEMA), Petra Korkiakoski (HAMK)
D1.4	Rural Attractiveness: Post Needs-Gathering Update	WP1	AREI	Report	Public	10	Pavel Kogut (21C), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Virpi Oksman (JIIP), Miloš Ulman (CULS)
D3.2	Innovation Hub: First Release	WP3	CCSS	Demonstrator	Public	10	Runar Bergheim (AVINET), Pavel Kogut (21C)
D1.5	Evaluation Methodology	WP1	JIIP	Report	Public	12	Pavel Kogut (21C), Christian Hartmann (JIIP), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Denis Kolokol (KAJO), Petra Korkiakoski (HAMK), Pawel Chmielinski (ERDN), Anne Gobin (VITO),

							Blagoja Mukanov (AG Futura)
D2.3	Final Text Mining Solution	WP2	KAJO	Other	Public	12	Karel Charvát (CCSS), Runar Bergheim (AVINET)
D4.3	Regional Library For Policy Evaluation	WP4	NÚVIT	Other	Public	12	Petra Korkiakoski (HAMK), Agnese Krievina (AREI)
D4.4	Needs-Policy Canvas	WP4	HAMK	Report	Public	12	Luigi Boccaccio (MurgiaPiu), Zuzana Pálková (SUA), Elena Horská (SUA)
D5.2	PoliRural Model (ed. 2)	WP5	22SISTEMA	Report	Public	12	Tuula Löytty (S&L), Ligita Melece (AREI)
D1.6	Framework Alignment & Theory Update (ed. 1)	WP1	21C	Report	Public	13	Patrick Crehan (CKA), Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA), Denis Kolokol (KAJO), Christian Hartmann (JIIP)
D3.3	System Dynamics Tool Technical Specifications	WP3	22SISTEMA	Report	Public	16	Denis Kolokol (KAJO), Patrick Crehan (CKA)
D7.3	Communication & Dissemination Plan Update	WP7	SPI	Report	Public	17	Pavel Kogut (21C), Pavel Šimek (CULS)
D1.7	Rural Attractiveness: Post-Evaluation Update	WP1	AREI	Report	Public	18	Pavel Kogut (21C), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA), Christian Hartmann (JIIP)
D1.8	Futures Outlook Methodology	WP1	CKA	Report	Public	18	Pavel Kogut (21C), Virpi Oksman (JIIP), Uri Marchaim (MIGAL), Kateřina Zachová (NUVIT), Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA),

							Anita Selicka (LLF), Anna Vatsanidou (NP), Tuula Löytty (S&L)
D1.9	Framework Alignment & Theory Update (ed. 2)	WP1	21C	Report	Public	18	Patrick Crehan (CKA), Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA), Virpi Oksman (JIIP), Marieta Okenkova (SUA)
D3.4	Innovation Hub: Second Release	WP3	CCSS	Other	Public	18	Runar Bergheim (AVINET), Pavel Kogut (21C)
D4.5	Perceived Effectiveness Of Rural Interventions, 12 Regions	WP4	JIIP	Report	Public	18	Natasa Ristovska (GGP), Pawel Chmielinski (ERDN)
D3.5	System Dynamics Tool: Initial Prototype	WP3	22SISTEMA	Demonstrator	Public	21	Karel Pánek (NUVIT), Anne Gobin (VITO)
D5.3	PoliRural Model (ed. 3)	WP5	22SISTEMA	Report	Public	19	Milla Anttila (HAMK), Jesús Estrada (TRAGSA)
D7.4	Draft Business Plan	WP7	21C	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	24	Marília Cunha (SPI), Tomáš Mildorf (P4A)
D1.10	Regional Recommendations	WP1	21C	Report	Public	28	Christian Hartmann (22SISTEMA), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Virpi Oksman (JIIP), Peter Vnucko (Agroinstitut), Anita Selicka (LLF), Lucie Nenckova (CCSS), Ioanna Kalyva (GAIA), Uri

							Marchaim (MIGAL), Mat Montalvo (Socialinnolabs), Natasha Ristovska (GGP)
D1.11	Regional Action Plan Template	WP1	JIIP	Report	Public	28	Pavel Kogut (21C), Patrick Crehan (CKA), Jakub Dvorský (VIPA SK), Jesús Estrada (TRAGSATEC), Uri Marchaim (MIGAL), Petra Korhikoski (HAMK), John O'Flaherty (MAC), Luigi Orsitto (CONF)
D3.6	System Dynamics Tool: Final Prototype	WP3	22SISTEMA	Other	Public	28	Pavel Kogut (21C), Miloš Ulman (CULS)
D5.4	PoliRural Model (ed. 4)	WP5	22SISTEMA	Report	Public	28	Uri Marchaim (MIGAL), Anne Gobin (VITO)
D5.5	A Dynamic Rural Development Model	WP5	CKA	Report	Public	28	Laila Gercane (VPR), Jakub Dvorský (VIPA SK)
D7.5	Report on dissemination and communication strategy	WP7	P4A	Report	Public	28	Laura Gavrilit (21C), Pavel Šimek (CULS)
D6.1	Pre-Intervention Case Study	WP6	VPR	Report	Public	29	Christian Hartmann (JIIP), Blagoja Mukanov (AG Futura)
D1.12	Framework Alignment & Theory Update (ed. 3)	WP1	21C	Report	Public	29	Patrick Crehan (CKA), Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA), Nicoleta Darra (AUA), Walter Mayer (CoO)

D6.2	Regional Action Plans	WP6	JIP	Report	Public	29	Krišjānis Veitners (VPR), John O'Flaherty (MAC)
D7.6	Communication & Dissemination Plan Update	WP7	SPI	Report	Public	29	Pavel Kogut (21C), Pavel Šimek (CULS)
D7.7	MOOC (1)	WP7	21C	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	30	Marília Cunha (SPI), Otakar Čerba (P4A)
D7.8	MOOC (2)	WP7	21C	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	32	Marília Cunha (SPI), Otakar Čerba (P4A)
D7.9	MOOC (3)	WP7	21C	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	34	Marília Cunha (SPI), Otakar Čerba (P4A)
D6.3	Post-Intervention Case Study	WP6	VPR	Report	Public	35	Christian Hartmann (JIIP), Peter Vnucko (Agroinstitut)
D3.7	PoliRural GitHub Account	WP3	TRAGSA	Other	Public	36	John O'Flaherty (MAC), Antoni Oliva (22SISTEMA)
D7.11	Final Business Plan	WP7	21C	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	36	Marília Cunha (SPI), Tomáš Mildorf (P4A)
D7.10	MOOC (4)	WP7	21C	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	36	Marília Cunha (SPI), Otakar Čerba (P4A)
D7.12	Toolbox	WP7	SPI	Report	Public	36	Pavel Kogut (21C), Miloš Ulman (CULS)
D8.2	IPR Roadmap	WP8	P4A	Report	Public	36	Zuzana Pálková (SUA), Nikolaos Marianos (NP)
D9.1	H – Requirement No. 1	WP9	CULS	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the	36	Tuula Löytty (S&L), Zuzana Pálková (SUA)

					Commission Services)		
D9.2	POPD – Requirement No. 2	WP9	CULS	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	36	Tuula Löytty (S&L), Zuzana Pálková (SUA)

Table 4 List of Deliverables and Internal Reviewers in a chronological order.

Annex 2: Assessment of Critical Risks

Table 5 Assessment of Critical Risks.

Risk #	Description of Risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Responsible Person (WP Leader)	Did you apply risk-mitigation measures? (yes/no)	Did the risk materialize? (yes/no)	Comments. If the risk-mitigation measures could not be applied, please explain why.
1	Poor commitment from partners leads to low quality work and missed deadlines/milestones	WP1 WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6 WP7 WP8 WP9	In case of problems with commitment, the coordinator will take proactive approach. Continuous communication, strong motivational leadership with clear responsibilities, detailed schedules and quick decision-making capabilities will help keep project momentum.	Pavel Šimek	Yes	No	
2	Key people in the consortium leave, creating a knowledge gap in the project	WP1 WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6 WP7 WP8 WP9	Plans and knowledge will be documented. Partners will be responsible, as outlined in the Consortium Agreement, for replacing members of staff with someone of the same standard.	Pavel Šimek	Yes	Yes	
3	Severe disagreement in the consortium lowers morale and affects outcomes	WP1 WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6 WP7 WP8	The coordinator is responsible to foresight, prevent and solve the case, but all partners are in charge of maintaining a good spirit. An honest but polite feedback will be promoted.	Pavel Šimek	Yes	No	
4	Pilots deviate from the plan and start carrying out only those	WP4 WP5 WP6	The project developed a standardised methodology to be followed by all	Patrick Crehan	No	No	To the extent that there are operational risks involved in the regional pilots, these should be dealt with by

	activities that they want and when they want them		pilots without exception. T8.2 is introduced to ensure no deviations from the plan happen and that pilots synchronise their activities to produce consistent results. Moreover, in its capacity as Assistant Pilot Manager, 21C will supervise pilot work during regular meetings to minimise any risk of deviation.				requiring those responsible for the pilots to submit their own action plan based on their adaptation of the model. This could then be reviewed by 21C or by a small advisory group involving the lead on TM and SDM as well as leads on the three phases (WP4, WP5 and WP6) to check its fitness for purpose.
5	Delays in transferring results in WP2 and WP3	WP2 WP3	The Technical Project Manager, WP2 and WP3 leaders follow readiness level on a weekly basis. In case of possible delay, the obstacles are removed.	Tommaso Sabbatini	Yes	No	
6	The solution of the text mining technology does not fully serve the project	WP2	The production method is incremental development. The continuous evaluation by the end users will indicate immediately the gaps and weaknesses.	Tommaso Sabbatini	Yes	No	
7	The users are not satisfied with the usability and service of Innovation Hub	WP3 WP7	Special attention is put into best possible user experience (UX) and serving the users by value adding and rich content. The former is attained by co-creation of Innovation Hub. Consortium members are involved into the development of the application (T3.1, T3.2). The latter is	Jiri Kvapil	Yes	No	

			the result of tasks in WP7 which enhance education, dissemination and exploitation.				
8	The number of Innovation Hub users is lower than expected	WP3 WP7	Each partner's duty is to actively use their social media channels to improve the visibility of the Innovation Hub. SPI as WP7 leader will remind all partners of the need of advertising the hub to stakeholder.	Marília Cunha	Yes	No data	
9	The usage of the System Dynamics Tool (SDT) appears to be too demanding or complicated	WP3	The SDT will be used hierarchically in two levels: The core model will be built by a small group of subject-matter experts. The adjustments into the core model correlate to the local needs and circumstances are done by pilots. The consortium level experts support pilot's measures. SDT granularity is a key to targeting of relevant information to relevant group of people the way they can understand it. End users are key partners in SDT development. System will be built according to their requirements, needs and abilities.	Jiri Kvapil	Yes	No	
10	Technical outputs face compatibility issues upon production,	WP2 WP3	The main technical outputs (platform, SDT, semantic explorer) will be designed with integration capacity	Tommaso Sabatini	Yes	No	

	affecting usability		in mind. This means that SDT and semantic explorer will be programmed in such a way as to allow their outputs to be easily transferable to the platform where they can be integrated for wider use.				
11	PoliRural fails to identify the most efficient instruments when it comes to accessing land	WP4 WP5 WP6 WP8	PoliRural will tackle the challenge in three fronts: (1) text mining enables to go through enormous mass of written documentation about the land accessing; (2) the participatory engagement via stakeholder panels ideate good, emergent and novel practices; (3) the clustering of pilots, which is based on similar practices, common needs and/ or foresight, widens the perspective and gives power into interventions.	Jesus Estrada	Yes	No	
12	Rural economies do not get sufficiently diversified as a result of PoliRural activities	WP6	Study areas with a strong need for diversification will co-create transition pathways using input from all regional stakeholders. Solutions will take into account historic situation, farm structure and type, market forces, environmental conditions, farmer's or household's composition and type, among others.	Uri Marchaim	Yes	No	

			Then, based on the assessment, specific measures can be promoted e.g. B&B, renewable energy, traditional crafts, eco-tourism. Supporting farmers and rural regions' economy will need the involvement of the partners.				
13	PoliRural doesn't succeed to align the agriculture policy into the direction in which enhancing vitality of rural is the main goal	WP4 WP5 WP6 WP7 WP8	PoliRural builds a computerised conceptual model of rural ecosystem at 12 pilots. The model and SDT system include at least 10 modules with relevant data. Each pilot would: (i) Formulate a goal that is meaningful for local stakeholders and local policy makers; (ii) adapt the pilot model in order to address that goal; (iii) the agricultural policy will naturally take its place within that context. The enhanced understanding of the agricultural ecosystem enables the change. The discussions and reflections at regional panels will be important part of continuous communication & dissemination.	Patrick Crehan	Yes	No	
14	The conceptual model created by System Dynamics Tool (SDT) does not facilitate decision making as expected	WP3 WP5	The subject-matter experts will support all pilots in the fields of technical and model issues. The rural model is going to provide a new view into agriculture. It will increase	Patrick Crehan	Yes	No	

			discussion, opinions and arguments. PoliRural enables to the stakeholder a learning experience. Together explore and further develop the Dynamic System Model.				
15	PoliRural's measures doesn't make rural living more attractive from the new entrant's point of view	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6	The PoliRural measures are carefully selected based on data. Pilots will utilize text mining technology to gain aggregated data. The Innovation Hub has European new entrants' arena in which best practises, tested business models and novel ideas are presented and shared. On the other hand, the Innovation Hub reviews also known barriers and problems which policy makers ought to tackle.	Pavel Kogut	No	No	PoliRural measures will be implemented at the end of the project, starting early 2023. The risks will be assessed when ex-durante results become available (D6.3)
16	Women, young and migrants are not covered, leading to missed objectives	WP4 WP5 WP6	Dynamic System Model includes data of women, young and migrants, and the pilots simulate their role and impact as a part of the system. The young farmers obtain a special attention at the pilots of Finland, Ireland, Belgium, Czech and Poland. Via the partners from the Balkans and the Middle East PoliRural gets insight of external migration flows.	Uri Marchaim	Yes	No	

Unforeseen risks (UR) – not part of the DoA							
UR 17	Low engagement of stakeholders in the PoliRural's activities	WP7	As WP7 leader, SPI as developed a communication and dissemination plan that will address measures to reach the target audiences	Marília Cunha	Yes	No	
UR 18	Poor language performance of the TM tool	WP2 WP4	To mitigate the risk of poor non-English language performance of the TM, first a proper adaptation of English-based solution will be made. Also to minimize the risk, appropriate local language research will be carried out using traditional desk work. The results of this will also provide a benchmark against which to evaluate the performance of the TM tool.	Denis Kolokol	Yes	No	
UR 19	Lack of involvement of the local communities	WP3	This risk may affect providing data for SDT but also identifying narratives, trends, key indicators, risks and institutional context. The project will work with authorities which may be able to make such data available one day. Mitigation will be done through the pilots and clearly presenting advantages of working with models as well as creating easy to use tools or models.	Jiri Kvapil	Yes	No	

UR 20	Failure to manage the impact of the regional pilot	WP4 WP5 WP6	For the success of the foresight activity, it is very important to manage the bottom-up activities needed to establish the relevance of the pilot and the challenges it addresses, in parallel with top-down activities needed to ensure the ability of policy makers and public administration to respond in an adequate and timely manner. In order to create conditions favorable for a high impact outcome of the pilots, the work of WP6 should start much sooner. This will be up to the pilot manager and WP4, WP5 and WP6 Leaders.	Patrick Crehan	Yes	No	
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